

HOW TO IMPROVE OUR TIME MANAGEMENT?

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Annotation: Knowing how to manage your time effectively is an important trait if you want to achieve goals faster and increased career growth. In this article we define how to use time wisely and stop wasting time.

Keywords: Time, value, manage the time, priority, efficient use of time, self-discipline, worldview, harmful habits

Time management involves planning and controlling the time we spend on specific tasks. This process allows us to give priority to certain tasks. This can lead to work more efficiently. Effective time management comes easier to some individuals than others. However, everyone can develop time management skills. All it takes is developing some healthy habits and exercising self-discipline.

To better manage our time, we need to understand how and why we may be wasting our time. For example, we live in a contemporary and developed era, and while this age gives us with many comforts, we do not value time. We can't make more time, but we can better manage our time to achieve more in the same amount of time. According to people who practice good time management techniques find that they are: being more productive, have more energy and motivation to accomplish goals, have more free time to enjoy hobbies and other positive towards of life. Feel better about themselves. We plan our day to the minute and second. However, we cannot achieve what we set out to do. After all, we do not feel sorry for our bad habits, the hours we spend surfing and we want to have a five-minute conversation with our mother on the "TELEPHONE". I have to work, we hurry to press the "red" button or mobile phone with accusations that I don't have time.

We come home in the middle of the night and rush to work again in the morning. Unfortunately, we do not have time to spend with our relatives, parents and children, to cheer them up. After all, the fact that the founder of the famous "Apple" company, billionaire Steve Jobs, When asked what he came to the conclusion of his life before his death, " Spend more time with each other" itself clarifies many puzzles. We can see the caption "Learning to manage time" in the title of the article. Now, ask yourself, is that really the case?!

Time passed like a river and we grew old. Now, think again, did time "rule" us or did we time? In order for us to "manage" time, we must first allocate our time properly, organize it and give up our harmful habits. After all, a product

with good quality will have a longer shelf life. We need to spend more time with our loved ones our family. One day, as we pass through this bright world, the time we spend in the memory of our loved ones will remain through our sweet and sincere conservations. Some social media users put terms like “Life is short, enjoy it” on their pages.

True, life is short, but every second counts. The time we spend in vain is accumulated over the years into days, months and years. I`m not saying don`t make fun of me with that. But the more we use our time, the more we will never regret it in the future.

We lose our health through harmful habits that harm your health, and through the hours we waste. We lose our precious wealth called time, and then we suffer through our unappreciated blessings. Hazrat Ismail Mursavi quoted the following words in his works: “If a person wastes his time or engages in activities that are not beneficial to his religion and the world, it means that he is in a state of imperfection or ignorance.”

Now, let`s turn to ourselves. Are we making good use of our time, or are the who are mired in ignorance? In short, to “manage” your time, do the following: Try wake up early and plan your day and definitely don`t forget to relax on time. Planning the different parts of your day such as tasks, meetings, meals and transport are all aspects of time management that can boost your productivity. Having a plan means there's a specific activity to complete at every point in time, helping you track your progress and complete tasks on schedule. Try to use it effectively even in situation that are common in our lives, such as waiting for a bus, getting stuck in traffic. Read more books. Because, the higher your worldview and spirituality, the more you learn to appreciate the divine blessings. If you follow this rule, you will “manage” your time efficiently.

Remember, your good deeds and the time productively will help you not only in this world but also in the hereafter.

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